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Development of Speaking Skills in English Language Learning in Universities

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***Abstract:** The subject of how speaking abilities are developed when teaching English in universities is brought up in this article. The author takes into account both the objective and subjective factors that influence how well a person learns to talk. The piece also touches on some of the challenges that come up in English classes when learning how to communicate.*

The article emphasizes the great importance and influence of the English teacher's educational level in preparing practical tasks on speech activities in university, as well as the ability to actively use their competencies in practice.

***Key words:** speaking skill, English language, competence, speaking activity, speech communication technique, learning process.*

INTRODUCTION

The ability to communicate verbally in a variety of situations via spoken or nonverbal signals is known as speaking skill, and it can be developed through language learning.

The compulsory skills of learning any foreign language include speaking, writing, listening, and reading (reading, writing, listening and speaking skills). Speaking ability difficulties can stem from a variety of objective and subjective factors.

English is the primary language used in modern society for cooperation, communication, and the sharing of knowledge and experiences. Therefore, while training specialists of different profiles, the primary objective of English language practice in higher education institutions should be identified as the development of communicative abilities, particularly speaking.

The goal of teaching speaking skills at universities is to help students become more adept at communicating orally in a variety of socially constructed contexts based on their own needs and interests.

Discussions

Some academics claim that "students' motivation, goal orientation, personal interest, speech and thinking activity, students' interaction in the learning process, contact (emotional, meaningful, personal), situational communication, and mastery of speech material" are all important components of being able to speak in a foreign language. These prerequisites are accumulated by the "functionality of the process, content, informativeness and complexity of the teaching material, novelty and expressiveness in the use of verbal and non-verbal means of communication." Furthermore, speaking is described as "a very multifaceted and complex phenomenon, mastering which is, first and foremost, the achievement of basic communicative competence" by other scientists.

We believe that a well-liked and effective toolkit for speaking skill development is watching documentaries, science documentaries, and feature films and videos in the classroom about the historical sites, natural wonders, cultural heritage, and geographic features of the target language nation. Students get the chance to become acquainted with lesser-known topics covered in printed teaching materials by watching films. It serves as a kind of reference material for class discussions about the videos they have seen, as well as a tool for written and oral tasks. Furthermore, various students may view the movie from different points of view, which can encourage less involved speakers to participate in the conversation.

I think that the quirks of students' memories also play a role in how well they master the art of speaking. The dominant analyst states that there are differences between motor, visual, aural, olfactory, tactile, emotional, and other forms of memory in the processes of memorizing, retaining, and reproducing content.

The primary objective of English language instruction is for teachers and students to be communicatively competent. This is achieved through effective classroom management, the use of active speech communication techniques by the teacher, assessing students' interest in learning, bridging the "language barrier," fostering a trusting environment in the classroom, and lowering students' level of apprehension when speaking in the language.

Clearly, the primary responsibility of the teacher is to engage the students in active speaking activities and to foster a culture of natural English conversation in the classroom. However, this is not always a simple task to accomplish.

The primary obstacles and reasons for acquiring fluency in spoken English are:

- Discomfiture on a psychological level. Causes include uncertainty and a fear of looking foolish in front of others;
- Absence of ideas or difficulty expressing them. Reasons: inadequate vocabulary and inability to focus;
- Speaking in Russian or Uzbek. Reasons: lack of active vocabulary on specific topics;
- Unequal degree of participation in the speaking process and different level of students' preparation. Reasons: some students are well prepared and fluent in English, while others have difficulties, speak little, or prefer to "sit unnoticed" because they cannot cope with labour-intensive

communication in English, as a result of which they get less language practice, do not get involved in collective speech communication, and lose motivation.

It goes without saying that a smaller class size and students who are closer to mastering speaking techniques will result in a more effective and successful learning experience.

Gaining professional knowledge also requires reading skills in English. In international publications, contracts, and directions, it is the language that is most frequently utilized.

Conclusion

The theoretical study's conclusion makes it abundantly evident that, in addition to having good methodological and technological resources, teachers must be able to actively use their knowledge of psychology and pedagogy to take into account the unique learning objectives of each student, as well as their age and individual characteristics.

Like all skills, public speaking skills do not develop on their own; they require instruction, proper preparation, and skilled management of the learning process, which involves active communication by each participant, taking into account all existing methods of developing public speaking skills. The author reported the accomplishment of the following outcomes based on the article's overall conclusions.

Theoretical research has led us to the conclusion that effective teaching of speaking skills requires teachers to possess not only good methodological and technological tools, but also the ability to actively apply their knowledge of psychology and pedagogy to account for the unique age characteristics of each student and their degree of motivation to learn.

In conclusion, speaking skills are essential for effective communication in personal and professional spheres. Developing these skills requires oral practice, language proficiency and cultural awareness. By paying close attention to these important factors and seeking opportunities for improvement, students are free to improve their public speaking abilities in the future and achieve greater success in various areas of life and certainly in their future careers.

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